

Fostering a Culture of Innovation: A Framework for Understanding Organizational Capacity for Innovation

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The churn rate of innovation has become constant with the emergence of globalization and technological advancements. The ability for organizations to maintain competitive advantage stems from many different veins; however, modern perspective and strategies indicate that for long-term sustainability, firms are scaling outside of their market (blue ocean strategy) or competing within their market (red ocean strategy). Both approaches require organizations to apply non-traditional practices to advance their strategic portfolio. These methods are centered around innovation from disruptive to fast-second and many other innovation methods. Essential components are needed to ensure these innovation strategies can transition ideas into action leading to positive change. The following article provides a framework for leaders to measure organizational capacity for innovation.

Keywords— innovation, planning, culture, leadership, strategy, framework

I. INTRODUCTION

The churn rate of innovation has become constant with the emergence of globalization and technological advancements. The ability for organizations to maintain competitive advantage stems from many different veins; however, modern perspective and strategies indicate that for long-term sustainability, firms are scaling outside of their market (blue ocean strategy) or competing within their market (red ocean strategy). Both approaches require organizations to apply non-traditional practices to advance their strategic portfolio. These methods are centered around innovation from disruptive to fast-second and many other innovation methods. Essential components are needed to ensure these innovation strategies can transition ideas into action leading to positive change. The following sections present the findings of a meta-analysis of innovation literature to conceptualize a framework for leaders to better understand organizational capacity for innovation.

II. INNOVATION LANDSCAPE CONCEPTUAL MODEL

Organizational Landscape

Organizations consist of a range of components that enable action. For the study, four organizational categories were identified as common themes throughout literature to represent culture, behavior, conditions, and capital. Table 1 describes each of the elements that comprise and define organizational landscape.

Table 1 *Organizational Landscape*

Category	Description
Mindset	Perceptions, knowledge, beliefs, and values that influence behavior
Resources	Financial, human, intellectual, network, and physical capital
Structure	Organizational hierarchy and operational plans
Support	Operational systems that promote and facilitate action

Meta-Analysis

A meta-analysis was conducted on models of innovation to identify common themes related to organizational structure, characteristics, and behaviors. The assessment of literature utilized a number of articles and trade journals with associated factors impacting innovation. Figure 1 presents the strategy used for developing classifications through the meta-analysis, whereby factors from literature (e.g., new ideas) were disaggregated into attributes (e.g., creativity, agility, openness, diversity of thought). The attributes were then grouped into ten classifications by clustering the attributes by commonalities.

Figure 1 *Meta-Analysis Strategy*

The findings from the content analysis yielded 423 different factors associated with organizational capacity, behaviors, and culture to support innovation. The 423 factors were analyzed and assigned attributes related to the categories of mindset, resources, support and structure. The analysis produced 1,992

attributes (an average of 4.7 per factor), and using cluster analysis, factors were organized into ten macro-level classifications.

Table 2 Overall Landscape

Classification	Factors	N
Openness	Access, transparency, trust	336
Collaboration	Cooperation, diversity, teams, synergy, relationships, human capital	299
Leadership	Vision, foresight, strategy	288
Experimentation	Creativity, ideas, risk, failure	203
Motivation	Support, empowerment, engagement, celebration	200
Learning	Inquiry, research, knowledge	170
Communication	Sharing, clear, consistent	158
Assets	Resources, systems, data	141
Agility	Nimble, adaptive, responsive	116
Roles	Responsibility, focus, dedication	81

The analysis in Table 2 shows that openness, collaboration, leadership, experimentation, motivation, and learning made up the majority (>75%) of classification linkages based on frequency of the factors. The findings support that an innovation ecosystem is embedded in the culture, values, behaviors and commitment to engaging individuals in cross-functional networks to solve problems and facilitate change.

Table 3 Landscape Classifications by Category

Classification	Mindset	Resources	Structure	Support
Openness	19.07%	13.32%	16.24%	17.93%
Collaboration	16.75%	13.32%	16.03%	14.34%
Leadership	11.34%	14.62%	13.03%	16.87%
Experimentation	13.40%	8.88%	11.11%	8.63%
Motivation	9.28%	10.97%	8.33%	11.02%
Inquiry	9.54%	7.83%	9.83%	7.57%
Communication	5.41%	5.74%	7.91%	10.36%
Assets	2.06%	12.53%	7.26%	6.77%
Agility	10.57%	5.74%	5.77%	3.45%
Roles	2.58%	7.05%	4.49%	3.05%

Additional cluster analyses were conducted on the four organizational landscape categories of mindset, resources, structure, and support to understand the distribution of factors across the different categories. The findings revealed that not all categories were equally represented across each of the ten classifications. Table 3 provides a synopsis of classification frequencies across the organizational categories. The results indicated that the most frequently occurring factors associated with fostering an innovative mindset included openness, collaboration, and experimentation. The assessment of organizational resources to support innovation included leadership, openness, and assets. Similar to the mindset category, the majority of the classifications that fell within organizational structure included openness, collaboration, leadership, and experimentation. The final assessment of

organizational support found that factors primarily clustered in openness, leadership, collaboration, motivation, and communication.

Conceptual Model

The results of the meta-analysis led to the development of a conceptual model as shown in Figure 2. The model reflects the distribution of classifications throughout an innovation landscape represented in Table 2.

Figure 2 Innovation Landscape Conceptual Model

A second model was created based on the distribution across the four organizational categories of mindset, resources, structure, and support as outlined in Table 3. The different models' distributions provide a weighted approach for measuring factors associated with classification of innovation. These models can be used to better understand the maturity of an organization's innovation landscape.

Instrument for Measuring Innovation Capacity

To better understand organizational capacity for innovation, a survey instrument was developed to gauge employee perception on the components of mindset, resources, structure, and support for innovation. The instrument consists of statements regarding the factors within the ten different classifications from Table 1. The instrument utilizes a five-point Likert scale to measure the level of agreement with each statement. A composite score is calculated based on the responses to determine the level of maturity across the four categories of the innovative landscape. The findings can be used to assess the overall landscape, including the classifications within each category.

III. IMPLICATION FOR APPLICATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Organizations are seeking ways to learn, mature, and progress into the future to meet external demand to maintain relevancy and competitiveness. While innovation continues to be a catalyst to achieve these aspirations, leaders are trying to understand ways to ensure the organizational ecosystem and culture are in alignment with innovative practices leading to positive outcomes. This study provides a conceptual framework

for leadership to recognize opportunities and gaps within an organization. The findings from this study can be used as a vehicle to inform and support movements for change.

Future research throughout different industries is needed to validate the innovation landscape instrument and model. Through continuous assessment, the tool and framework can be refined for use by different populations and industries.

IV. DISCUSSION

In today's highly rapidly changing and competitive market, it is essential that leadership understand their organization's capacity to compete in current and future markets. The conceptual model from this study allows for leaders to identify gaps within an organization in support of innovation to allow for focused strategies to support cultural shifts. While the conceptual framework and instrument provide direction to better understanding organizational capacity to innovate, continuous validation is needed. Therefore, future research needs to be conducted to validate the instrument across different industries.

References

- Bastedo, M. N. (2007, April). Bringing the state back in: promoting and sustaining innovation in public higher education. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 61(2), 155-170. doi:10.1111/j.1468-2273.2007.00344.x
- Carpenter, H. (2009, September 8). Crowdsourced or elite unit innovation [Blog post]. Retrieved from <https://bhc3.com/2009/09/08/crowdsourced-or-elite-unit-innovation/>
- Carpenter, H. (2014, November 5). Rate your company's innovation culture [Blog Post]. Retrieved from <https://blog.hypeinnovation.com/rate-your-companys-innovation-culture>
- Damanpour, F. (1991). Organizational Innovation: A Meta-Analysis of Effects of Determinants and Moderators. *Academy of Management Journal*, 34(3), 555-590. Retrieved from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/256406>
- Daum, K. (2016, November 4). The best leaders avoid these 7 innovation myths [Blog post]. Retrieved from <https://www.inc.com/kevin-daum/the-best-leaders-avoid-these-7-innovation-myths.html>
- Dyer, J. & Gregersen, H. (2012, September 5). Frequently asked questions about the innovation premium [Blog Post]. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/innovatorsdna/2012/09/05/frequently-asked-questions-about-the-innovation-premium/#39a1c88e5d96>
- Dyer, J. & Gregersen, H. (2015, August 19). How we rank the world's most innovative companies 2015 [Blog Post]. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/innovatorsdna/2015/08/19/how-we-rank-the-worlds-most-innovative-companies-2015/#27d0b2695f8c>
- Fallon, K. (2016, August 4). Top 10 keys to innovation success the best companies use [Blog Post]. Retrieved from <http://www.pivotalinnovation.com/Blog/ArtMID/564/ArticleID/13/Top-10-Keys-to-Innovation-Success-the-Best-Companies-Use>
- Godin, B. (2005). The linear model of innovation: the historical construction of an analytical framework. Project on the History and Sociology of S&T Statistics Working Paper No. 30. Retrieved from http://www.csiic.ca/PDF/Godin_30.pdf
- Greenwald, T. (2011, November 28). Seven keys to business innovation: how to create breakthroughs [Blog post]. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/tedgreenwald/2011/11/28/seven-keys-to-business-innovation-how-to-create-breakthroughs/#3387c9633cd9>
- Hecht, B. (2013, January 10). Collaboration is the new competition. *Harvard Business Review*. Retrieved from <https://hbr.org/2013/01/collaboration-is-the-new-compe>
- Hype. (N. D.) Innovation Culture: 25 behaviors affecting your program's success. Retrieved from <https://www.hypeinnovation.com/learn/reports/innovation-culture-assessment>
- Kaasa, A, & Vadi, M. (2008). How does culture contribute to innovation? Evidence from European countries. Retrieved from <https://www.mtk.ut.ee/sites/default/files/mtk/RePEc/mtk/febpdf/febawb63.pdf>
- Kania, J. & Kramer, M. (Winter 2011). Collective impact. *Stanford Social Innovation Review*. Retrieved from https://ssir.org/articles/entry/collective_impact
- Kaplan, S. (N. D.). The complete guide to innovation metrics – how to measure innovation for business growth [Blog post]. Retrieved from <http://www.innovation-point.com/innovationmetrics.htm>
- Knowles, C., Hansen, E., & Dibrell, C. (2008). Measuring firm innovativeness: development and refinement of a new scale. *Journal of Forest Products Business Research* 5(5), 1-24. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Clay_Dibrell/publication/258559444_Measuring_Firm_Innovativeness_Development_and_Refinement_of_a_New_Scale.pdf
- Omerzel, D. G. (2016). The impact of entrepreneurial characteristics and organizational culture on innovativeness in tourism firms. *Managing Global Transitions: International Research Journal*, 14(1), 93-110. Retrieved from http://www.fm-kp.si/zalozba/ISSN/1581-6311/14_93-110.pdf
- Preskill, H. & Beer, T. (2012). Evaluating social innovation. Retrieved from <https://www.fsg.org/publications/evaluating-social-innovation>
- Skillicorn, N. (2016, March 18). What is innovation? [Blog post]. Retrieved from <https://www.ideatovalue.com/inno/nickskillicorn/2016/03/innovation-15-experts-share-innovation-definition/>

Turró, A., Urbano, D. & Peris-Ortiz, M. (2013, September 30). Culture and innovation: The moderating effect of cultural values on corporate entrepreneurship. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change* 88(2014), 360–369. Retrieved from http://www.academia.edu/8557030/Culture_and_innovation_The_moderating_effect_of_cultural_values_on_corporate_entrepreneurship

University Innovation Alliance. (N.D.) Vision and prospectus. Retrieved from <http://www.theuia.org/sites/default/files/UIA-Vision-Prospectus.pdf>

Von Hippel, E. (2005). Introduction and overview. *Democratizing innovation*. (pp. 1-17). Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press. Retrieved from <http://web.mit.edu/evhippel/www/books/DI/DemocInn.pdf>